

Estimation of response expectation bounds under parametric p-boxes by combining Bayesian global optimization with unscented transform

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ABSTRACT

In engineering analysis, propagating parametric probability boxes (p-boxes) remains a challenge since a computationally expensive nested solution scheme is involved. To tackle this challenge, this paper proposes a novel optimization-integration method to propagate parametric p-boxes, mainly focusing on estimating the lower and upper bounds of structural response expectation for linear and moderately nonlinear problems. A model-based optimization scheme, named Bayesian global optimization, is first introduced to explore the space of distribution parameters. Subsequently, an efficient numerical integration method, named unscented transform, is employed to estimate the response expectation with a given set of distribution parameters. Compared to existing optimization-integration methods, the proposed method has three advantages. First, the response expectation

25 bounds are successively estimated, allowing for the reuse of samples generated from the lower
26 bound estimation in the upper bound estimation. Second, the approximation error introduced
27 by the numerical integration method is considered. Third, computational efficiency in both the
28 optimization and integration processes is improved. Four applications are investigated to validate
29 the effectiveness of the proposed method, showing its ability to balance computational efficiency
30 and accuracy when evaluating response expectation bounds.

31 **KEYWORD**

32 Imprecise probability propagation, Parametric probability box, Response expectation bounds,
33 Bayesian global optimization, Unscented transform, Gaussian process

34 **INTRODUCTION**

35 Practical engineering problems are often rife with aleatory uncertainties that are irreducible and
36 stem from random nature, such as the uncertainties in material properties, external loads, operating
37 environments and etc. In many cases, the information for describing such uncertainties can be
38 insufficient, ambiguous, fragmentary, or indeterminate (Beer et al. 2013). In this regard, epistemic
39 uncertainties that result from a lack of knowledge or information should also be considered. Such
40 mixed uncertainty can be characterized by the imprecise probability model such as the parametric
41 probability box (p-box) model (Ferson and Hajagos 2004; Faes et al. 2021). For a parametric
42 p-box model, aleatory uncertainty is represented by a set of probability distributions with known
43 distribution types, while epistemic uncertainty is reflected by the imprecise distribution parameters
44 that can be described by intervals. In order to reflect the influence of input imprecise probabilities
45 on structural responses, imprecise probability propagation is of great significance in engineering
46 structural analysis.

47 In general, the state-of-the-art methods for propagating parametric p-boxes can be classified into
48 two categories: double-loop methods and single-loop methods. As a straightforward approach, the
49 double-loop method treats the epistemic and aleatory uncertainties through a nested loop structure.
50 Double-loop Monte Carlo simulation (DLMCS) (Bruns and Paredis 2006) samples different sets

51 of distribution parameters in the outer loop, and for each distribution parameter set, Monte Carlo
52 simulation (MCS) is performed to estimate the output of interest in the inner loop. DLMCS works
53 regardless of nonlinear properties and dimensionalities of the problem at hand. However, it is quite
54 computationally expensive, since both loops require a considerably large number of samples in
55 order to ensure the estimation accuracy of the output of interest. Although some improved DLMCS
56 methods, such as interval Monte Carlo method (Zhang et al. 2010; Zhang et al. 2012) and the
57 vertex-based DLMCS (Vertex-MCS) (Xiao et al. 2016), are developed to reduce the number of
58 samples in total, their scopes of application and efficiency are limited.

59 To improve the computational efficiency, an outer-loop optimization can be adopted, where
60 imprecise distribution parameters are treated as design variables to be optimized and the lower and
61 upper bounds on the output of interest are regarded as two separate optimization objectives. In the
62 inner loop, the output of interest at a certain design point can be estimated by aleatory uncertainty
63 propagation methods. Take the example of capturing the bounds on a response expectation,
64 numerical integration methods can be adopted in the inner loop to evaluate the response expectation
65 under fixed distribution parameters. The integration of outer-loop optimization and inner-loop
66 numerical integration methods can be collectively referred to as optimization-integration methods.
67 Typical optimization-integration methods are the optimized parameter sampling (OPS) (Bruns and
68 Paredis 2006; Bruns 2006), optimized univariate dimension-reduction method (OUDRM) (Liu et al.
69 2018) and optimized sparse grid numerical integration method (OSGNI) (Liu et al. 2019). Such
70 existing methods rely on gradient-based optimizers, which can easily converge to a local optimum.
71 In this sense, the resulting response expectation bounds may be underestimated. Although some
72 global optimization algorithms, like the genetic algorithm (Pedroni and Zio 2015), can help mitigate
73 this issue, the optimization process requires a large number of objective function calls, which can be
74 time-consuming when dealing with objective functions that are expensive to evaluate. In the inner
75 loop, some efficient numerical integration methods, such as univariate dimension-reduction method
76 (Liu et al. 2018) and sparse grid numerical integration (Liu et al. 2019), are employed. Nevertheless,
77 the computational efficiency within the inner loop can be further enhanced, especially for linear

78 and moderately nonlinear problems. Additionally, existing optimization-integration methods do
79 not account for the approximation error introduced by numerical integration methods, potentially
80 resulting in inaccuracies in the derived response expectation bounds. Furthermore, these methods
81 are unable to fully leverage the data generated by the lower or upper estimation that has already
82 been performed.

83 On the other hand, to alleviate the computational burden of the double-loop framework, many
84 single-loop methods have been recently developed, such as the extended Monte Carlo simula-
85 tion (EMCS) (Wei et al. 2014), non-intrusive imprecise stochastic simulation (NISS) (Wei et al.
86 2019), non-intrusive imprecise probabilistic integration (NIPI) (Wei et al. 2021b), collaborative
87 and adaptive Bayesian optimization (CABO) (Wei et al. 2021a), and parallel Bayesian quadrature
88 optimization (PBQO) (Dang et al. 2022a). Note that existing single-loop methods typically rely
89 on constructing an augmented uncertainty space consisting of both aleatory and epistemic uncer-
90 tainties, which increases the dimensionality to be dealt with. Although some single-loop methods
91 such as CABO and PBQO may require less response function calls compared with double-loop
92 methods, it becomes difficult to estimate the output of interest for problems with high-dimensional
93 augmented uncertainty space. Besides, EMCS and NISS are not capable for propagating parametric
94 p-boxes with distribution parameters that are supported in a wide range.

95 Therefore, there is still a need to develop a method for parametric p-box propagation with not
96 only reasonable accuracy and efficiency, but also fine applicability. The main focus of this paper
97 is on capturing the response expectation bounds that reflect the effect of epistemic uncertainty on
98 the statistical characteristics of the response. A new optimization-integration method is presented
99 to estimate the response expectation bounds, especially for linear and moderately nonlinear prob-
100 lems. The proposed method combines two advanced and efficient strategies to greatly reduce the
101 computational efforts. Specifically speaking, to facilitate the optimization process, a model-based
102 optimization scheme, named Bayesian global optimization (BGO) (Jones et al. 1998), is employed.
103 By using the BGO, the original expensive-to-evaluate objective function can be predicted by an
104 cheap-to-evaluate Bayesian model. To consider the effects of approximation errors introduced by

105 numerical integration in estimating the response expectation, noisy Gaussian process (GP) model
106 is adopted in this study. Such GP model can be updated adaptively according to an effective
107 improvement strategy, so as to obtain the globally effective optima, i.e., the optimal distribution
108 parameters corresponding to the response expectation bounds, with fewer computational efforts.
109 When estimating response expectation on the set of distribution parameters obtained from the
110 optimization process, a highly efficient numerical integration method, called unscented transform
111 (UT) (Julier and Uhlmann 1997b; Wan and Van Der Merwe 2000; Jia et al. 2013), is implemented.
112 UT is able to provide estimated results up to third degree of algebraic accuracy, which should
113 be acceptable for linear and moderately nonlinear problems. Besides, the number of simulations
114 grows only linearly with the dimension of p-box variables. It is worth mentioning that compared
115 with existing optimization-integration methods, the proposed method takes into account the ap-
116 proximation errors brought by UT. Moreover, the proposed method estimates the lower and upper
117 response expectation bounds in a sequential manner, where the samples generated for the lower
118 bound evaluation can be further reused for the upper bound evaluation to reduce unnecessary waste
119 of computational efforts.

120 The remaining of the paper is organized as follows: Section "Problem statement" introduces the
121 mathematical formulation of the response expectation bounds considering input variables described
122 by parametric p-boxes. Section "Proposed method" presents the proposed optimization-integration
123 approach that combines the BGO with the UT. Section "Test examples" investigates four test
124 examples to illustrate the feasibility of the proposed method. Conclusions are given in section
125 "Concluding remarks".

126 To enhance readability, a list of acronyms used in this paper is provided in Table 1.

127 **PROBLEM STATEMENT**

128 Consider a response function that describes the input-output relationship of a structural system
129 as $Y = g(\mathbf{X})$. Here, $g(\cdot)$ represents a deterministic, continuous and real-valued mapping function;
130 $\mathbf{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_s}\}$ is an n_s dimensional input vector of variables, where each variable is
131 characterized by a parametric p-box model; Y denotes a scalar output of interest, which is also a p-

132 box variable. Let us denote $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n_\theta})$ as n_θ -dimensional imprecise distribution parameter
 133 vector. The epistemic uncertainty in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is represented by a hyperrectangle, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]$, where
 134 $\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = (\underline{\theta}_1, \underline{\theta}_2, \dots, \underline{\theta}_{n_\theta})$ denotes the lower bound and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = (\bar{\theta}_1, \bar{\theta}_2, \dots, \bar{\theta}_{n_\theta})$ is the upper bound. Then,
 135 the joint probability density function (PDF) of X can be represented by $f(\mathbf{x}|\boldsymbol{\theta})$. For convenience,
 136 all variables in X and distribution parameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are assumed to be mutually independent.

137 Under the above setting, the probability distribution and any statistical moments of Y are also
 138 functions of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Taking the expectation of Y as an example, it can be written as:

$$139 \quad m(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{n_s}} g(\mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{x}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (1)$$

140 where $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ represents the expectation of Y , the value of which depends on the value of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. It
 141 is noted that for some practical engineering applications, the analysts may be more interested in
 142 obtaining the bounds on $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ than in obtaining expressions for the response expectation function
 143 over the entire domain of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. This is because the response expectation bounds enable to provide a
 144 possible range reflecting the effect of epistemic uncertainty on expectation of Y (Wei et al. 2021a).
 145 In addition, evaluating the bounds on response expectation can be much more easier than capturing
 146 the overall behavior of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ over the full domain of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. In this regard, this paper focuses on the
 147 estimation of the response expectation bounds.

148 The lower and upper bounds of response expectation can be obtained by finding the minimal
 149 and maximal values of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ within the hyperrectangle $[\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]$, which can be expressed as:

$$150 \quad \underline{m} = \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} m(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (2)$$

$$151 \quad \bar{m} = \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} m(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (3)$$

153 where \underline{m} and \bar{m} denote the lower and upper bounds of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, respectively. In the following, the
 154 optimal distribution parameter corresponding to \underline{m} is denoted as $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}$, and the optimal distribution
 155 parameter corresponding to \bar{m} is represented as $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}$.

156 Note that for most cases, the analytical expression of $m(\theta)$ is usually difficult and even impossi-
157 ble to obtain due to underlying complexity of Eq. (1). Hence, directly finding analytic solutions for
158 the minimum and maximum values according to Eqs. (2)-(3) is rather difficult. Alternatively, we
159 can resort to the optimization-integration method such that θ can be first searched by optimization
160 and the response expectation at a certain θ found during the optimization process is then estimated
161 based on a numerical integration method. Since the response function involved in Eq. (1) is
162 usually a black-box function that is expensive to evaluate, a computationally efficient optimization-
163 integration method that calls the response function as few as possible is highly desired. At the same
164 time, such method should also enable to provide estimated response expectation bounds with ac-
165 ceptable accuracy. To achieve this aim, a novel optimization-integration method will be developed
166 in the following.

167 **PROPOSED METHOD**

168 In this section, a new optimization-integration method is developed to estimate the lower
169 and upper bounds of $m(\theta)$ with reasonable accuracy and efficiency, where \underline{m} and \bar{m} are separately
170 estimated one after the other. Note that the proposed method is able to make full use of the available
171 information such that data obtained from the lower bound estimation can be further reused in the
172 upper bound estimation, and thus avoiding unnecessary computational effort. Specifically, a model-
173 based optimization method, named Bayesian global optimization (Jones et al. 1998), is employed
174 in order to explore the space of distribution parameters. At each θ found during the optimization
175 process, one highly efficient numerical integration method, named unscented transform (Julier and
176 Uhlmann 1997b; Wan and Van Der Merwe 2000; Jia et al. 2013), is introduced to evaluate $m(\theta)$.

177 **Bayesian global optimization**

178 By making use of BGO, our basic idea is to assume a Bayesian model to $m(\theta)$, and then
179 update the Bayesian model successively with additional observations according to an efficient infill
180 sampling criterion (Jones et al. 1998; Dang et al. 2022b). Such infill sampling criterion enables
181 to fully exploit the available observations, and strike a good tradeoff between exploitation and
182 exploration for the selection of the new updating observations. In the following, the Bayesian

183 model and infill sampling criterion adopted in the optimization process of proposed optimization-
 184 integration method are introduced in detail.

185 *Gaussian process model*

186 Following a Bayesian approach, the expensive-to-evaluate response expectation function can be
 187 treated with a Bayesian model. Commonly, Gaussian process (GP) model (Williams and Rasmussen
 188 2006) is adopted in the BGO. Note that for most realistic modeling situations, we cannot obtain
 189 the true value of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, but only a noisy version of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$. In this regard, we assume that the noisy
 190 version of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, denoted as $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, is equal to the true response expectation function $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ plus an
 191 additional noise ϵ such that $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = m(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \epsilon$, where ϵ is assumed to follow a zero-mean Gaussian
 192 distribution with variance σ_ϵ^2 . The true response expectation $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is assigned a GP prior such that
 193 $m_0(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \sim \text{GP}(\beta(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}'))$, where $\beta(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and $\kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}')$ are the prior mean and covariance (also
 194 called kernel) functions, respectively. There are many different forms of prior mean and covariance
 195 functions, which can be found in Ref. (Williams and Rasmussen 2006). In this work, a constant
 196 prior mean is adopted such that $\beta(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \beta_0$ and $\beta_0 \in \mathbb{R}$. The squared exponential kernel function
 197 is employed here, which can be expressed as:

$$198 \quad \kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}') = \sigma_0^2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}')^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}')\right), \quad (4)$$

199 where σ_0^2 denotes the overall variance; $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(l_1^2, l_2^2, \dots, l_{n_\theta}^2)$ is a diagonal matrix and $l_i, i =$
 200 $1, \dots, n_\theta$ is the length scale in the i -th dimension. Under these settings, a total of $n_\theta + 3$ free
 201 parameters are involved inside the GP model, which are referred to as the hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\psi} =$
 202 $\{\beta_0, \sigma_0, \sigma_\epsilon, l_1, \dots, l_{n_\theta}\}$ and can be inferred from a set of observations.

203 Suppose that we have obtained \mathcal{N} noisy observations. Denote such training dataset as $\mathcal{D} =$
 204 $\{\boldsymbol{\Theta}, \hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta})\}$, where $\boldsymbol{\Theta} = \{\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}; \dots; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(\mathcal{N})}\}$ is a sample matrix with size $(\mathcal{N} \times n_\theta)$, and $\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) =$
 205 $\{\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}), \dots, \hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(\mathcal{N})})\}^T$ is an $(\mathcal{N} \times 1)$ response expectation vector whose components have been
 206 evaluated. Based on the training dataset \mathcal{D} , the hyperparameters can be optimally determined by

207 maximizing the log marginal likelihood function (Williams and Rasmussen 2006):

$$208 \quad \boldsymbol{\psi}^\star = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\psi}} \left(\log \left(p \left(\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) \mid \boldsymbol{\Theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi} \right) \right) \right), \quad (5)$$

209 where

$$210 \quad \log \left(p \left(\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) \mid \boldsymbol{\Theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi} \right) \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) - \beta_0 \right)^\top \left(\mathbf{K} + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \left(\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) - \beta_0 \right) - \frac{1}{2} \log \left(|\mathbf{K} + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I}| \right) - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{2} \log(2\pi), \quad (6)$$

211 in which \mathbf{K} is an $(\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N})$ covariance matrix with (i, j) -th entry as $\kappa \left(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)} \right)$; \mathbf{I} is an $(\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N})$
 212 identity matrix. For more details, the interested readership may refer to Ref. (Williams and
 213 Rasmussen 2006).

214 Once the hyperparameters are determined, a posterior distribution of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ can be obtained by
 215 conditioning on \mathcal{D} . At a new observation $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the posterior of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ follows a normal distribution
 216 such that $m_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \sigma_{\mathcal{N}}^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \right)$. Here, the posterior mean $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is employed as the
 217 predictor of response expectation in the optimization process, and the posterior variance $\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}^2(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is
 218 the measure of prediction uncertainty. $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and $\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}^2(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ can be expressed in closed form:

$$219 \quad \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \beta(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\Theta}) \left(\mathbf{K} + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \left(\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) - \beta(\boldsymbol{\Theta}) \right), \quad (7)$$

$$220 \quad \sigma_{\mathcal{N}}^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) - \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\Theta}) \left(\mathbf{K} + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} \right)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\Theta})^\top, \quad (8)$$

222 in which $\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\Theta})$ is a $(1 \times \mathcal{N})$ covariance vector between $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Theta}$, and its i -th component is
 223 $\kappa \left(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} \right)$; $\beta(\boldsymbol{\Theta})$ is an $(\mathcal{N} \times 1)$ expectation vector with i -th component as $\beta \left(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(i)} \right)$.

224 *Expected improvement criterion*

225 To infer the response expectation bounds \underline{m} and \bar{m} from fewer training samples, an efficient
 226 infill sample strategy combined with the GP model is desired. Note that the aim of such strategy
 227 is to find the promising points where to evaluate the objective function by extracting as much as
 228 possible knowledge from the current posterior GP. Along this line, the expected improvement (EI)

230 criterion (Jones et al. 1998) could be a good choice. By maximizing the EI, new update points
 231 can be selected by exploiting the best existing solutions from the GP model and exploring the
 232 undeveloped design space that may contain potential optima. In this regard, here we adopt the EI
 233 criterion to find θ_{\min} and θ_{\max} that respectively corresponding to \underline{m} and \bar{m} , where the lower bound
 \underline{m} is estimated first and the upper bound \bar{m} is evaluated subsequently.

234 **EI criterion for lower bound optimization** Let $\theta_{\min}^{\star} = \arg \min_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{\hat{m}(\theta^{(j)})\}$ be the current
 235 best solution to lower expectation bound \underline{m} obtained from the training dataset \mathcal{D} . We are aiming
 236 to search for a new sample point θ that enables to bring about an improvement beyond the current
 237 lower response expectation bound at point θ_{\min}^{\star} . The expectation of such improvement conditional
 238 on Θ , denoted as $\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\theta)$, can be expressed as (Jones et al. 1998):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E} \left[\max \left(\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta), 0 \right) \right] = \begin{cases} \mathbb{E} \left[\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta) \right], & \text{if } \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta) < \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

240 where $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) = \min_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{\hat{m}(\theta^{(j)})\}$. The analytical expression of the above EI function can
 241 be derived as (Jones et al. 1998):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\theta) = \left(\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta) \right) \Phi \left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)}{\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)} \right) + \sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta) \phi \left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta_{\min}^{\star}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)}{\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)} \right), \quad (10)$$

243 where $\Phi(\cdot)$ and $\phi(\cdot)$ represent the cumulative distribution function (CDF) and PDF of the standard
 244 normal distribution, respectively. The new sample point, denoted as θ_{\min}^+ , is determined by
 245 maximizing $\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\theta)$, i.e.,

$$\theta_{\min}^+ = \arg \max_{\theta \in [\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]} \mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\theta). \quad (11)$$

247 The first term in Eq. (10) prefers the point related to smaller $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)$, while the second term in Eq.
 248 (10) prefers the sample point that has larger prediction uncertainty $\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\theta)$. Hence, a good tradeoff
 249 between model exploitation and exploration can be achieved by the EI criterion. Note that since

250 $\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is usually multi-modal, additional global optimization algorithms are desired to solve Eq.
 251 (11). Herein, one recently developed global optimization algorithm, called Equilibrium Optimizer
 252 (EO) algorithm (Faramarzi et al. 2020), is employed.

253 A stopping criterion is required here to indicate when to stop the lower bound optimization
 254 scheme. One common stopping criterion is to check whether the value of maximum EI is relatively
 255 small or not, i.e., $\max_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} \mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) < \mathcal{E}_m$, where \mathcal{E}_m denotes the stopping tolerance that is
 256 usually prescribed by the users based on their requirement. Since the magnitude of $\mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is
 257 usually unknown in advance, an improved stopping criterion that measures the relative error of the
 258 maximal EI (Huang et al. 2006) is adopted here, such as:

$$259 \frac{\max_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} \mathcal{L}_{\min}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) - \min_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})} < \mathcal{E}_1, \quad (12)$$

260 where $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})$, $1 \leq j \leq N$ is the estimated expectation in the current \mathcal{D} ; the stopping tolerance
 261 \mathcal{E}_1 is suggested to take the magnitude of 0.1% – 1%. If Eq. (12) is not satisfied, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+$ and
 262 the corresponding response expectation $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+)$ evaluated by a numerical integration method
 263 described in Section 4 are added to \mathcal{D} , and then a new round of lower bound optimization is
 264 implemented based on the enriched \mathcal{D} . To avoid possible premature convergence to suboptimal
 265 solutions, it is preferable to use a delayed judgement, i.e., to stop only when Eq. (12) is successively
 266 satisfied several times (e.g., three times).

267 **EI criterion for upper bound optimization** Once the lower bound optimization scheme ends,
 268 the upper bound optimization starts based on the training dataset \mathcal{D} obtained from lower bound
 269 optimization. In this manner, the number of update points needed for upper bound estimation can
 270 be reduced and the current available training data can be further reused. Similarly, let $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star} =$
 271 $\arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})\}$ be the current best solution to the upper expectation bound \bar{m} observed
 272 so far. Then, the location of next evaluation $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is determined by maximizing the EI over the current

273 maximum posterior response expectation $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star}) = \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})\}$, i.e.,

$$274 \quad \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^+ = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} \mathcal{L}_{\max}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (13)$$

275 where $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^+$ denotes the new update point associated with the upper response expectation bound.

276 The corresponding EI function, denoted as $\mathcal{L}_{\max}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, is defined in closed form (Dang et al. 2022b):

$$277 \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\max}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) &= \mathbb{E} \left[\max \left(\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star}), 0 \right) \right] \\ &= \left(\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star}) \right) \Phi \left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star})}{\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})} \right) + \sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \phi \left(\frac{\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^{\star})}{\sigma_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

278 Here, EO algorithm (Faramarzi et al. 2020) is also employed to find $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^+$.

279 Similarly, the normalized version of stopping criterion for upper bound optimization scheme is
280 adopted (Huang et al. 2006):

$$281 \quad \frac{\max_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in [\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]} \mathcal{L}_{\max}^{\text{EI}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)}) - \min_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(j)})} < \mathcal{E}_2, \quad (15)$$

282 where the stopping tolerance \mathcal{E}_2 can take the same value as \mathcal{E}_1 for convenience. If Eq. (15) is not
283 satisfied, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^+$ and corresponding response expectation $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\max}^+)$ estimated according to Section 4
284 are added to the training dataset \mathcal{D} . Then, another round of upper bound optimization is performed
285 based on the enriched \mathcal{D} . The optimization scheme stops only when Eq. (15) is satisfied for three
286 times consecutively.

287 **Remark.** Note that it is also possible to perform the upper bound optimization first and then the
288 lower bound optimization. In this case, the training dataset \mathcal{D} obtained from the upper bound
289 optimization will be used as the initial training dataset for the lower bound optimization.

290 Unscented transform

291 As observed from Eq. (1), the evaluation of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ at a fixed design point $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ becomes a determin-
292 istic but still difficult-to-evaluate integration. In this regard, one may resort to use the numerical

293 integration method to approximate such deterministic integration. Denote the approximated solu-
 294 tion of $m(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ at a fixed observation $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ as \hat{m} . Using the numerical integration method, \hat{m} can be
 295 expressed as:

$$296 \quad \hat{m} = \sum_{r=1}^{N_q} w_r g(\boldsymbol{\chi}_r), \quad (16)$$

297 in which N_q is the number of integration points; $\boldsymbol{\chi}_r$ is the r -th integration point, and w_r is the
 298 corresponding r -th weight.

299 Under this setting, there is a need for an efficient method to evaluate \hat{m} . The unscented transform
 300 (UT) (Julier and Uhlmann 1997b; Wan and Van Der Merwe 2000; Jia et al. 2013) is adopted in our
 301 work, since UT is computationally more efficient while maintaining acceptable accuracy, compared
 302 to MCS, univariate dimension reduction method, and sparse grid numerical integration utilized
 303 in existing optimization-integration methods (Bruns and Paredis 2006; Liu et al. 2018; Liu et al.
 304 2019). The UT was first introduced by Jeffrey Uhlmann (Julier and Uhlmann 1997b) in the field of
 305 nonlinear Kalman filter, which enables to calculate the expectation of a random vector propagated
 306 through a nonlinear transformation. The basic idea of UT is to first select a finite number of sample
 307 points, also known as sigma points, transform these sigma points by a nonlinear transformation,
 308 and finally perform a weighted summation of the transformed sigma points to obtain an estimate
 309 of the response expectation. The sigma points are obtained by sampling in the original Gaussian
 310 distribution according to certain rules, and the corresponding weights satisfy the results of the
 311 weighted sum of the sigma points with the same mean and variance of the Gaussian distribution.
 312 Accordingly, the sigma points and corresponding weights can be respectively given by (Julier and
 313 Uhlmann 1997b; Julier and Uhlmann 1997a):

$$314 \quad \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_1 = [0, \dots, 0]^T, & w_1 = \frac{\kappa}{n_s + \kappa}, \quad r = 1 \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}_r = \sqrt{n_s + \kappa} \boldsymbol{e}_{r-1}, & w_r = \frac{1}{2(n_s + \kappa)}, \quad r = 2, \dots, n_s + 1 \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}_r = -\sqrt{n_s + \kappa} \boldsymbol{e}_{r-n_s-1}, & w_r = \frac{1}{2(n_s + \kappa)}, \quad r = n_s + 2, \dots, 2n_s + 1, \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

315 where \boldsymbol{e}_{r-1} is the n_s -dimensional unit vector with the $(r-1)$ -th element being 1; κ is the scaling

316 factor that enables to tune the accuracy of moment approximations. According to Ref. (Julier
 317 and Uhlmann 1997b), it is suggested to take $\kappa = 3 - n_s$ for sigma points following the Gaussian
 318 distribution. In this manner, we have

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\gamma}_1 = [0, \dots, 0]^T, & w_1 = \frac{3-n_s}{3}, & r = 1 \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}_r = \sqrt{3}\mathbf{e}_{r-1}, & w_r = \frac{1}{6}, & r = 2, \dots, n_s + 1 \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}_r = -\sqrt{3}\mathbf{e}_{r-n_s-1}, & w_r = \frac{1}{6}, & r = n_s + 2, \dots, 2n_s + 1. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

320 Based on the above sigma points and corresponding weights, the response expectation can be
 321 estimated such that:

$$\hat{m} = \sum_{r=1}^{N_q} w_r g \left(\Gamma^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\gamma}_r | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right), \quad (19)$$

323 where $N_q = 2n_s + 1$, which is highly efficient to evaluate the response expectation; $\Gamma^{-1} (\cdot | \boldsymbol{\theta})$ rep-
 324 represents the isoprobabilistic transformation that transform sigma points from the standard Gaussian
 325 space to the original input random space. In this regard, the integration points can be regarded as the
 326 transformed sigma points, where the transformation relationship is $\boldsymbol{\chi}_r = \Gamma^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\gamma}_r | \boldsymbol{\theta})$, $r = 1, \dots, N_q$.
 327 It is worth mentioning that responses corresponding to those N_q sigma points involved in Eq. (19),
 328 i.e., $g \left(\Gamma^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\gamma}_r | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right)$, $r = 1, \dots, N_q$, can be evaluated in parallel.

329 Note that the sigma points are generated by matching the moments of Gaussian random variables
 330 up to the second order. In addition, all odd-ordered moments of a Gaussian variable are zero.
 331 Therefore, the UT is able to estimate response expectation at a fixed $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ up to the third order, regardless
 332 of the dimension of input variables (Julier and Uhlmann 1997a; Wan et al. 2001). Nevertheless,
 333 the UT is somehow difficult to adapt to problems with strong nonlinearities (Julier 2002). In
 334 this regard, it is reasonable to expect that the use of UT to evaluate the response expectation can
 335 have acceptable accuracy and efficiency for linear and moderately nonlinear problems. However,
 336 the approximation error introduced by UT needs to be considered, as it may affect the accuracy
 337 of the outer-loop optimization within the distribution parameter space. To take into account the
 338 approximation error in the optimization process, the estimated response expectation at a fixed

339 design point θ , i.e., $\hat{m}(\theta^{(i)})$, is treated as a noisy observation in the training dataset \mathcal{D} .

340 **Step-by-step procedure**

341 Once both the stopping criteria associated with the lower and upper bounds are satisfied in the
 342 optimization process, the lower and upper response expectation bounds can be obtained from the
 343 final training dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\Theta, \hat{\mathcal{M}}(\Theta)\}$, such as:

$$344 \quad \underline{m} = \min_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\theta^{(j)}), \quad (20)$$

$$345 \quad \bar{m} = \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{m}(\theta^{(j)}), \quad (21)$$

347 where the current N is the sample size of the final obtained \mathcal{D} . Accordingly, the total number
 348 of response function calls required by response expectation bound estimation is $N = \mathcal{N} \times N_q =$
 349 $\mathcal{N} \times (2n_s + 1)$. To distinguish the stopping criterion involved in lower bound estimation with that
 350 involved in upper bound estimation, the first criterion is named criterion 1, and the second is named
 351 criterion 2 in the following. A flowchart of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 1. To illustrate
 352 the procedure of proposed method, here we take the evaluation of the lower bound of response
 353 expectation as an example, and a brief procedure is summarized as follows:

354
 355 **Step 1:** Initialization. Set the initial sample size \mathcal{N}_{ini} and stopping tolerance \mathcal{E}_1 . Create
 356 the initial training set $\mathcal{D} = \{\Theta, \hat{\mathcal{M}}(\Theta)\}$ of size \mathcal{N}_{ini} by two steps. First, randomly sample \mathcal{N}_{ini}
 357 distribution parameters θ from the hyperrectangle $[\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ by adopting the Latin hypercube sampling
 358 (LHS) method, and form $\Theta = \{\theta^{(1)}, \theta^{(2)}, \dots, \theta^{(\mathcal{N}_{\text{ini}})}\}^T$. Then, employ the UT to estimate \mathcal{N}_{ini}
 359 response expectations $\hat{m}(\theta)$ at each component of Θ , and accumulate these resultant estimated
 360 expectations as $\hat{\mathcal{M}}(\Theta) = \{\hat{m}(\theta^{(1)}), \dots, \hat{m}(\theta^{(\mathcal{N}_{\text{ini}})})\}^T$. Denote the current sample size as \mathcal{N} , where
 361 $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}_{\text{ini}}$ at present.

362 **Step 2:** Optimization for finding θ_{min}^+ . This step involves first training a noisy GP model
 363 of $m(\theta)$ based on the current training set \mathcal{D} such that $m_N(\theta) \sim \text{GP}(\mu_N(\theta), \sigma_N^2(\theta))$. The
 364 training of noisy GP model is realized by using the *fitrgp* function in the Matlab ‘‘Statistic

and Machine Learning Toolbox", where the initial value for the noise standard deviation σ_ϵ is set to be 0.002. Then, the current best lower bound $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^\star)$ is specified by $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^\star) = \min\{\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(1)}), \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(2)}), \dots, \mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(\mathcal{N})})\}$. The new update point $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+$ is selected from the hyper-rectangle $[\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}]$ by maximizing EI over $\mu_{\mathcal{N}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^\star)$, where the EO algorithm is employed.

Step 3: Check the stopping criterion 1. To accommodate stochastic evaluations, criterion 1 in Eq. (12) is checked by three times successively. If the criterion 1 is satisfied, end the updating process and output the current \mathcal{D} as the initial training set for upper bound optimization; otherwise, go to step 4.

Step 4: Evaluation of the response expectation at $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+$. The response expectation at the new update point $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+$, i.e., $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+)$, is evaluated by the UT according to Eq. (19). A total of $N_q = 2n_s + 1$ sigma points and corresponding weights involved in UT are generated by Eq. (18).

Step 5: Enrichment of the training dataset. The new update point $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+$ and corresponding expectation value $\hat{m}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\min}^+)$ are added into the training set \mathcal{D} . Then, set $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N} + 1$ and go to Step 2 to perform a new round of optimization.

TEST EXAMPLES

In this section, four test examples are investigated to verify the feasibility of the proposed method. In all cases, the size of initial training dataset takes $\mathcal{N}_{\text{ini}} = \min\{2n_\theta, 10\}$, and the stopping tolerances for both lower bound and upper bound estimations take $\mathcal{E}_1 = \mathcal{E}_2 = \mathcal{E} = 0.002$. To illustrate the advantages of the proposed method, two existing optimization-integration methods, i.e., OSGNI (Liu et al. 2019) and OUDRM (Liu et al. 2018), are performed for comparison in all examples. Both of these two methods employ the *fmincon* algorithm with sequential quadratic programming (SQP) method in Matlab for searching the optimal distribution parameters in the optimization process, where the termination tolerances for first-order optimality and step size are set to be 10^{-6} . At a certain set of distribution parameters, the OSGNI adopts the sparse grid numerical integration method (SGNI) (Heiss and Winschel 2008) using the nested quadrature rule with Gaussian weights to evaluate the response expectation, where the accuracy level k_{acc} representing the order of polynomial used for fitting is prescribed. The OUDRM employs the

392 univariate dimension reduction method (UDRM) (Rahman and Xu 2004) for expectation estimation,
 393 in which the number of Gauss-Hermite points used, denoted as N_G , is given in advance. For all
 394 examples, $k_{acc} = 3$ and $N_G = 6$, unless otherwise specified in the example. Furthermore, in the first
 395 two examples, we also compare the results obtained by DLMCS (Bruns and Paredis 2006) method,
 396 Vertex-MCS (Dong and Shah 1987) method, and OPS (Bruns and Paredis 2006) method. Note
 397 that the outer loop of OPS is also performed by adopting MATLAB function *fmincon* with SQP
 398 algorithm, while the inner loop of OPS employs the MCS with 10^4 runs. All the above methods
 399 are implemented in MATLAB on the same computer with Intel Core i7-11800H at 2.30 GHz and
 400 32GB of RAM.

401 **Example 1: a two-dimensional toy example**

402 A two-dimensional toy example is first investigated, whose response function is given by:

$$403 \quad y = g(x_1, x_2) = 1 + \frac{(x_1 - 1)^3}{9} + \frac{(x_2 - 1)^3}{16}, \quad (22)$$

404 where x_1 and x_2 are both Gaussian random variables with non-deterministic distribution parameters,
 405 i.e., mean and standard deviation. The mean parameters of x_1 and x_2 , denoted as μ_1 and μ_2 , take
 406 the same interval value $[-1, 3]$. And both the standard deviation parameters of x_1 and x_2 , i.e., σ_1
 407 and σ_2 , are set as $[0.5, 3]$.

408 In this example, the lower and upper bounds of response expectation are estimated by the analyt-
 409 ical method, DLMCS, Vertex-MCS, OPS, OSGNI, OUDRM and the proposed method. Since this
 410 example is simple, the OUDRM employs the UDRM using $N_G = 2$ Gauss-Hermite points in the
 411 inner loop. To examine the robustness, each method is repeatedly performed 10 times. The average
 412 results obtained by each method and the corresponding average total number of response function
 413 calls (denoted as N) are presented in Table 2, along with the average number of simulations associ-
 414 ated with the lower and upper bounds (denoted as N_L and N_U). Additionally, the coefficients of vari-
 415 ation (COVs) for the estimated bounds are reported. The analytical solution of response expectation
 416 can be easily derived as $\mu_{true} = 1 + \frac{1}{9} (\mu_1 - 1) [(\mu_1 - 1)^2 + 3\sigma_1^2] + \frac{1}{16} (\mu_2 - 1) [(\mu_2 - 1)^2 + 3\sigma_2^2]$,

417 which provides the analytical lower and upper bounds of response expectation as $\underline{m} = -9.7639$ and
 418 $\overline{m} = 11.7639$, respectively. Note that since the UT has third-order algebraic accuracy, the response
 419 expectation estimated using the UT should be accurate for any given set of distributed parameters
 420 in this example. Compared with the analytical results, the proposed method obtains both the lower
 421 and upper bounds of response expectation in a robust and accurate manner. On average, only a
 422 total of $N = N_L + N_U = 76 + 27 = 103$ response function calls are required, where N_{ini} is included
 423 in N_L . The OSGNI and OUDRM enable to provide quite accurate bound results, however, these
 424 two existing methods require more response function calls compared with the proposed method.
 425 In this sense, more computational efforts are required by the OSGNI and OUDRM. In addition,
 426 as observed from Table 2, the Vertex-MCS and OPS are able to give relatively accurate bounds,
 427 but both require more than one million samples, which is considerably expensive. Unfortunately,
 428 the traditional and widely used DLMCS is unable to obtain accurate lower and upper bounds on
 429 response expectation. Besides, the COVs of DLMCS results are larger than those by other methods.

430 **Example 2: a 120-bar spatial truss structure**

431 Example 2 investigates a 120-bar spatial truss structure subjected to seven vertical nodal loads
 432 (Dang et al. 2021), shown in Figure 2. In this figure, the nodes that bear vertical loads are marked
 433 with red circles and numbers. The vertical displacement of the top node of this structure is of
 434 interest in this example, which is analyzed by a finite element software, OpenSees. Each member is
 435 modeled as a truss element. A total of 48 nodes and 120 elements are involved in the finite element
 436 model. The Young's modulus E_0 , cross-sectional area of element A and seven vertical nodal loads
 437 (i.e., $P_0, P_2, P_4, P_6, P_8, P_{10}, P_{12}$) are considered as input variables. Among them, E_0, A and P_0 are
 438 p-box variables, and $P_2, P_4, P_6, P_8, P_{10}$ and P_{12} are aleatory variables. The description of these
 439 nine input variables is provided in Table 3.

440 In this example, the expectation bounds of the response of interest are estimated by the Vertex-
 441 MCS, DLMCS, OPS, OSGNI, OUDRM and the proposed method, where the corresponding results
 442 are given in Table 4. We take the result obtained by the Vertex-MCS as the reference. As observed,
 443 the lower and upper response expectation bounds by the proposed method accord fairly well with

444 the reference bounds. In addition, only $N = N_L + N_U = 247 + 57 = 304$ response function calls are
445 required in the proposed method, which is within affordable computational limits. Unfortunately,
446 other selected double-loop methods, i.e., the DLMCS, OPS, OSGNI and OUDRM, can only provide
447 narrower bounds on the response expectation but require much more computational efforts.

448 **Example 3: a jet engine turbine blade**

449 The third example consists of a jet engine turbine blade under pressure loading, as illustrated in
450 Fig. 3a (MATLAB 2022). The turbine blade is governed by two mechanical boundary conditions,
451 namely the pressure loads P_1 and P_2 on the pressure and suction sides caused by the surrounding
452 high-pressure gases, and the fixed Dirichlet boundary condition on the left side. The model is
453 discretized by adopting the linear tetrahedral elements with maximum element size as 0.01 m, as
454 shown in Fig. 3b. A total of 21252 nodes and 11794 elements are involved. This turbine blade is
455 assumed to be made by the nickel-based alloy (NIMONIC 90) material, where the Young's modulus,
456 coefficient of thermal expansion and Poisson's ratio are represented by E , α and ν , respectively.
457 Here, the maximum von Mises stress of the turbine blade caused by high pressure from surrounding
458 gases is the response of interest, which can be obtained by performing linear stress analysis using
459 the Matlab Partial Differential Equation (PDE) Toolbox (MATLAB 2022). Five p-box variables,
460 i.e., $\{E, \alpha, \nu, P_1, P_2\}$, are considered in this example, of which the mean and standard deviation
461 parameters are all bounded by intervals. The detailed description of these p-box variables is listed
462 in Table 5. Fig. 3c shows a resultant von Mises stress nephogram obtained by performing one
463 structural analysis with all input variables to be fixed at the midpoint of their mean parameter
464 intervals. As seen, the maximum von Mises stress happens at the tip of the turbine blade.

465 The OSGNI, OUDRM, Vertex-MCS and proposed method are employed in this example to
466 estimate the lower and upper bounds of response expectation, whose results are provided in Table
467 6. It can be observed that the proposed method is able to obtain the response expectation bounds
468 that are almost identical to those by the Vertex-MCS. However, much fewer response function
469 calls (specifically $N = 143 + 33 = 176$) are required by the proposed method, indicating that the
470 proposed method has comparable accuracy but higher computational efficiency. In comparison,

471 the OSGNI and OUDRM give narrower response expectation bounds but cost considerably larger
472 computational efforts. Note that although this example involves only linear stress analysis, the large
473 number of discrete elements results in a relatively long time for one evaluation of the response.
474 We record the total computational times for all the methods implemented in this example, which
475 are also given in Table 6. It is found that the proposed method takes much less time than OSGNI,
476 OUDRM, and Vertex-MCS. Thus, it indicates that the proposed method is more computationally
477 efficient for this example.

478 **Example 4: a crash box in the vehicle**

479 Last example investigates the frontal impact problem of a crash box impacted by a moving
480 planar impactor. The crash box is an important energy absorbing component installed at the front
481 of the vehicle, which determines the crashworthiness and ensures the safety of the vehicle. A
482 quarter of a symmetric crash box (Reid 1998) shown in Fig. 4 is considered in this example,
483 which is analyzed by the LS-DYNA software in symmetric multiprocessing (SMP) version. The
484 crash box is built as a tube with an uncertain shell thickness t , and adopts a steel-like material
485 modeled by a piecewise linear plastic model with Poisson's ratio as 0.3, yield strength as 207 MPa,
486 mass density as 7830 kg/m^3 , strain rate model as Cowper-Symmonds with parameter $C = 40$
487 and $p = 5$, and an uncertain Young's modulus E . The lower end of the crash box is fixed. A
488 planar impactor, modeled as a rigid wall with imprecisely known mass M_{wall} and initial velocity
489 v_{wall} , crushes the crash box from the top downwards. Three triggers are applied to the crash box
490 in order to achieve desired energy absorption and deformation pattern. The LS-DYNA keyword
491 **CONTACT_AUTOMATIC_SINGLE_SURFACE* is applied to formulate the contact between
492 the impactor and the crash box. The simulation is terminated when the impactor stops moving
493 or the total time reaches 15.01 ms. This example involves a total of 4 p-box variables with
494 8 imprecise distribution parameters, i.e., $\{M_{\text{wall}}, v_{\text{wall}}, E, t\}$, whose detailed description is listed
495 in Table 7. Fig. 4c shows the deformation of the crash box under rigid wall impact, where
496 $\{M_{\text{wall}}, v_{\text{wall}}, E, t\} = \{800 \text{ kg}, 8.94 \text{ m/s}, 200 \text{ GPa}, 2 \text{ mm}\}$. As observed, the impacted crash box
497 deforms in a folding mode without global bending, showing its good ability to absorb the impact

498 energy. In addition, under the same input conditions, the force-displacement curve of the rigid wall
499 in the negative Z direction is illustrated in Fig. 5, which indicates that the investigated crash box
500 undergoes irreversible nonlinear buckling deformation, and has a relatively strong nonlinearity.

501 The output response of interest is the average force of the complete force-displacement curve
502 measured at the rigid wall. Note that this example also requires a long computational time
503 to perform a simulation. In order to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method, a
504 comparison is made between the results obtained from the proposed method, the Vertex-MCS,
505 OSGNI and UDRM, as summarized in Table 8, alongside the respective total computational times.
506 As observed, the proposed method enables to provide lower and upper bounds on the expectation of
507 the averaged rigid wall force that are quite close to those of Vertex-MCS, while the proposed method
508 requires much fewer response function calls, specifically $N = 162 + 63 = 225$. In comparison,
509 OSGNI and OUDRM produce narrower response expectation bounds but require a larger number
510 of simulations. Moreover, the computational time for the proposed method is 2134.01 s, while the
511 Vertex-MCS, OSGNI and OUDRM require 13245.27 s and 6639.07 s, respectively. Hence, this
512 example illustrates that the proposed method can be applied not only to linear and weakly nonlinear
513 problems, but also to problems with relatively strong nonlinearity.

514 **CONCLUDING REMARKS**

515 In this paper, an efficient optimization-integration method is developed for estimating the
516 lower and upper bounds of response expectation for linear and moderately nonlinear problems
517 with inputs characterized by parametric p-boxes. The proposed method combines the Bayesian
518 global optimization (BGO) with a highly efficient numerical integration method named unscented
519 transform (UT), to sequentially evaluate lower and upper bounds on response expectations. An
520 adaptively refined noisy Gaussian process (GP) model is adopted to explore the space of distribution
521 parameters considering the approximation error introduced by UT. Besides, the sequential design
522 strategy of BGO allows the proposed method to reuse the samples generated by the lower bound
523 estimation in the upper bound estimation. In the process of response expectation at a given set of
524 distribution parameters, the UT is quite efficient and can obtain the estimates of response expectation

525 up to third accuracy. Four test examples are investigated to demonstrate the applicability to both
526 linear and moderately nonlinear problems. For all of these examples, the results obtained by the
527 proposed method use a reasonable number of response function calls. In addition, the resultant
528 response expectation bounds are almost the same as the provided reference results, showing the
529 effectiveness of the proposed method. Compared with some existing double-loop methods such
530 as DLMCS, Vertex-MCS, OPS, OSGNI and OUDRM, the proposed method is able to acquire
531 the results with acceptable accuracy and higher computational efficiency. It can also be observed
532 from the four test examples that the accuracy of the proposed method is mainly affected by the
533 complexity and nonlinearity of the problem at hand. For simpler problems, increasing the level
534 of epistemic uncertainty does not affect the accuracy, while for more complex problems, a higher
535 level of epistemic uncertainty tends to have a greater impact on the accuracy of the results.

536 Admittedly, since the approximated expectation by the UT has only up to third order accuracy,
537 the proposed method is not suitable for addressing strong nonlinear problems and evaluating
538 higher-order response moments. To mitigate this, we are actively exploring alternative numerical
539 integration methods, such as the mixed degree cubature scheme (He et al. 2022), to capture higher-
540 order moments within our framework. Besides, the BGO in the optimization process still suffers
541 from the so-called "curse of dimensionality" problem, i.e., it may perform poorly for problems with
542 more than 20 dimensions. Future work will focus on a time-saving method for evaluating bounds
543 on higher-order response moments that is applicable to higher dimensional and stronger nonlinear
544 problems.

545 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

546 All data, models, or code that support the findings of this study are available from the corre-
547 sponding author upon reasonable request.

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TABLE 1. List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BGO	Bayesian global optimization
CABO	Collaborative and adaptive Bayesian optimization
COV	Coefficient of variation
DLMCS	Double-loop Monte Carlo simulation
EI	Expected improvement
EMCS	Extended Monte Carlo simulation
EO	Equilibrium optimizer
GP	Gaussian process
MCS	Monte Carlo simulation
NIPI	Non-intrusive imprecise probabilistic integration
NISS	Non-intrusive imprecise stochastic simulation
OPS	Optimized parameter sampling
OSGNI	Optimized sparse grid numerical integration method
OU DRM	Optimized univariate dimension-reduction method
p-box	Probability box
PBQO	Parallel Bayesian quadrature optimization
PDE	Partial differential equation
PDF	Probability density function
SGNI	Sparse grid numerical integration method
SMP	Symmetric multiprocessing
SQP	Sequential quadratic programming
UDRM	Univariate dimension-reduction method
UT	Unscented transform
Vertex-MCS	Vertex-based Monte Carlo simulation

TABLE 2. Comparison of results by different methods (Example 1)

Method	\underline{m}	COV of \underline{m}	\overline{m}	COV of \overline{m}	N
Analytical	-9.7639	-	11.7639	-	-
Vertex-MCS	-9.7318	0.79%	11.7839	0.47%	16×10^5
DLMCS	-8.1585	4.75%	9.8238	5.97%	$10^4 \times 10^4$
OPS	-9.8778	0.37%	11.6531	0.29%	$(896 + 1063) \times 10^4 = 1.959 \times 10^7$
OSGNI	-9.7639	0.00%	11.7639	0.00%	$270 + 270 = 540$
OU DRM	-9.7639	0.00%	11.7639	0.00%	$140 + 27 = 167$
Proposed	-9.7639	0.00%	11.7639	0.00%	$76 + 27 = 103$

Note: COVs relates to the coefficients of variation; for DLMCS and vertex-MCS, $N = N_L \times N_U$; for OPS, OSGNI, OU DRM and proposed method, $N = N_L + N_U$.

TABLE 3. Description of input variables (Example 2)

Variable	Unit	Description	Distribution	Mean	Standard deviation
E_0	MPa	Young's modulus	Truncated Normal	[164800, 247200]	[2060, 10300]
A	mm ²	Cross section area	Truncated Normal	[900, 1100]	[1, 5]
P_0	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	[180, 220]	[2, 10]
P_2	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2
P_4	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2
P_6	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2
P_8	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2
P_{10}	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2
P_{12}	kN	Vertical load	Lognormal	200	2

Note: Truncated Normal means the values are all positive.

TABLE 4. Comparison of results by different methods (Example 2)

Method	\underline{m} (MPa)	\overline{m} (MPa)	N
Vertex-MCS	25.2309	51.1475	64×10^4
DLMCS	25.9681	49.2774	$10^3 \times 10^4$
OPS	27.8320	46.2661	$(57 + 75) \times 10^4 = 132 \times 10^4$
OSGNI	27.8153	46.2762	$1304 + 1304 = 2608$
OU DRM	27.8153	46.2762	$432 + 368 = 800$
Proposed	25.2393	51.1061	$247 + 57 = 304$

TABLE 5. Description of input variables (Example 3)

Variable	Unit	Description	Distribution	Mean	Standard deviation
E	Pa	Young's modulus	Truncated Normal	$[204.3, 249.7] \times 10^9$	$[227, 1135] \times 10^9$
α	1/K	Coefficient of thermal expansion	Truncated Normal	$[1.143, 1.397] \times 10^{-5}$	$[1.270, 6.350] \times 10^{-7}$
ν	-	Poisson's ratio	Truncated Normal	$[0.243, 0.297]$	$[0.270, 1.350] \times 10^{-2}$
P_1	Pa	Pressure load	Truncated Normal	$[45, 55] \times 10^4$	$[5, 25] \times 10^3$
P_2	Pa	Pressure load	Truncated Normal	$[405, 495] \times 10^3$	$[45, 225] \times 10^2$

TABLE 6. Comparison of results by different methods (Example 3)

Method	\underline{m} (MPa)	\overline{m} (MPa)	N	CPU time
Vertex-MCS	93.8542	118.8419	1024×10^3	804115.49 s
OSGNI	97.0640	115.0664	$1122 + 1122 = 2244$	7464.80 s
OU DRM	97.0640	115.0664	$660 + 572 = 1232$	5402.62 s
Proposed	94.1447	118.6347	$143 + 33 = 176$	821.28 s

Note: CPU time represents the total computational time.

TABLE 7. Description of input variables (Example 4)

Variable	Unit	Description	Distribution	Mean	Standard deviation
M_{wall}	kg	Mass of the rigid wall	Truncated Normal	[760, 840]	[8, 40]
v_{wall}	m/s	Velocity of the rigid wall	Truncated Normal	[8.10, 9.90]	[0.09, 0.45]
E	GPa	Young's modulus	Truncated Normal	[195, 205]	[2, 10]
t	mm	shell thickness	Truncated Normal	[1.90, 2.10]	[0.02, 0.10]

TABLE 8. Comparison of results by different methods (Example 4)

Method	\underline{m} (kN)	\overline{m} (kN)	N	CPU time
Vertex-MCS	7.7243	9.4776	256×10^2	166403.64 s
OSGNI	8.0823	9.2635	$1353 + 297 = 1650$	13245.27 s
OU DRM	8.0893	9.2379	$672 + 216 = 888$	6639.07 s
Proposed	7.8018	9.4252	$162 + 63 = 225$	2134.01 s

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Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed method

(a) Geometry of the turbine blade (dimensions in m)

(b) Meshed model of the turbine blade

(c) Von Mises stress nephogram of structural analysis

Fig. 3. Geometry, mesh diagram and von Mises stress nephogram of the jet engine turbine blade under pressure loads

Fig. 4. Front and right view of the meshed model of a quarter of the crash box, and the deformation of the crash box under planar rigid wall impact

Fig. 5. Force-displacement curve of the planar impactor in the negative Z direction